

Using the Ride Adjuster and the Wand in the Moth Class

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During several training sessions, the Authors faced the problem of managing the Ride Height Adjuster and Wand setting, reckoning the difficulties a novice might encounter. For this reason, the following short guide is provided in an attempt of helping young sailors to have a first idea of the topic.

Sailing | Hydrofoil | MothClass |

Introduction: Lift and Drag

This guide aims to give a first hint about the setting of the **Ride Height Adjuster** (RHA hereafter) and the **Wand** to beginner and advanced athletes. The aim is to help moth sailors understand the impact of these components and how to set them effectively in relation to each other for optimal performance.

Fig. 1. Simple representation of the RHA-Wand System. [3]

Even before we plunge inside the topic, the authors want to introduce a well-known, yet not straightforward concept: the lift-to-drag ratio (or L/D Ratio) (1). As we all know, lift and drag are two sides of the same coin, and we are usually more interested in the first one be it about sails or foils. Just to make an aeronautical example, an airplane flying at cruise speed in level flight generates a lift equal to its weight. The higher the lift, the higher the payload. While cruising the plane flies at a constant speed so that the thrust is equal to the drag generated by the wings. Under the same generated lift, a low-drag aircraft requires low thrust and that's why faster planes can afford smaller wings (see the North American X-15 (2)).

Designation	Diagram	$C_{L_{max}}$	α at $C_{L_{max}}$ (degrees)	L/D at $C_{L_{max}}$	$C_{m_{ac}}$	Reference NACA
Basic airfoil Clark Y		1.29	15	7.5	-.085	TN 459
30c Plain flap deflected 45°		1.95	12	4.0	-	TR 427

Fig. 2. Extract from various NASA Technical Reports [4] [5].

Fig. 3. The relation between lift and drag (coefficients) under different flap settings [6].

Figure 2 shows how the L/D ratio is roughly twice when the flaps are retracted while, in addition, Figure 3 demonstrates that a wing without flaps achieves a reduced lift but comes with the significant advantage of much lower drag. Given this, it is clear how a slow plane with flaps and slats down will be able to fly at very low speeds, generating a sufficient lift at the cost of a great drag, going on a very low L/D Ratio. On the other hand, a plane flying at higher speed will not need to increase the wing surface with slats and flaps and the right amount of lift will come with a very low drag and a very high L/D Ratio.

The Rod

Before discussing the Wand and RHA, let's talk about an important component called the Rod. This component is either a carbon tube or a titanium bar with the purpose to connect the Wand and the Main Foil to ensure they can smoothly operate together. At the end of the ROD, there are two uniballs, with the most popular one

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249	Coordinating the Wand and Ride Adjuster	will not be efficient for high-speed purposes (especially when you	311
250	Proper coordination between the wand and ride adjuster is	are no longer in light winds).	312
251	essential for optimal performance. In summary, the general		313
252	sequence is to set the ride adjuster to establish the desired ride		314
253	height, and then adjust the wand to fine-tune the main foil flap.		315
254	This approach ensures that you have a stable platform with the		316
255	desired lift characteristics for optimal performance in Moth foiling.		317
256	Once the Wand length is set, play with the ride adjuster "on" or		318
257	"off" to find the perfect balance between lift, stability, and speed		319
258	based on the prevailing wind conditions. A final piece of advice		320
259	recalls the L/D Ratio. Remember that a full-flapped configuration		321
260	will improve stability and lift, but it will also create high drag and		322
261			323
262			324
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265	2 Dennis R. Jenkins, Tony Landis, and Jay Miller. AMERICAN X-VEHICLES. An Inventory—X-1 to X-50. NASA History Office. 2003. NASA SP-2003-4531.		327
266	3 Hillman, Alan. The Foiling Dinghy Book: Dinghy Foiling From Start To Finish. Fernhurst Books, 2018. ISBN-10: 9781912177035.		328
267	4 Weick, Fred E and Platt, Robert C. Wind-tunnel tests on model wing with Fowler flap and specially developed leading-edge slot. Langley Memorial Aeronautical Laboratory. 1933. NACA-TN-459.		329
268	5 Weick, Fred E. and Shortal, Joseph A. The effect of multiple fixed slots and a trailing-edge flap on the lift and drag of a Clark Y airfoil. Langley Memorial Aeronautical Laboratory. 1933. NACA-TR-427.		330
269	6 Jr, Edward A. Haering. Airdata calibration of a high-performance aircraft for measuring atmospheric wind profiles. NASA Ames Research Center. 1990. p.230. 28th Aerospace Sciences Meeting.		331
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